

NATIONAL SEMINAR ON

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: STRENGTHS AND CHALLENGES

(SPONSORED BY RAJIV VIDYA MISSION (SSA), HYDERABAD, ANDHRA PRADESH)

COMPENDIUM

Dr. M.T.V. NAGARAJU

ORGANISING SECRETARY

DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION

Dr. B.R.AMBEDKAR OPEN UNIVERSITY

Road No. 46, Jubilee Hills

HYDERABAD - 500 033 (A.P.)

Dr. B.R. AMBEDKAR OPEN UNIVERSITY
HYDERABAD- 500 033 (A.P.)

DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION

Cordially invites you to the inauguration of

NATIONAL SEMINAR
ON

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION STRENGTHS AND CHALLENGES

(Sponsored by RAJIV VIDYA MISSION (SSA), HYDERABAD, A.P.)

On Thursday, the 07th MARCH, 2013 at 10.30 AM

E-Class Room, STML Building,
University Campus, Road No.46, Jubilee Hills, Hyderabad

Chief Guests

Smt. V. USHA RANI

IAS

State Project Director, Rajiv Vidya Mission (SSA), AP

Dr. P. PRAKASH

Vice-Chancellor, Dr. BRAOU

Guest of Honour & Key Note Address

Prof. GHANTA RAMESH

Chairman (BoS in Education), Kakatiya University, Warangal (A.P.)

President of the function

Prof. N. VENKATANARAYANA

Director (Academic) & Dean I/c (FoE), Dr. BRAOU

Dr. M.T.V. NAGARAJU
Organising Secretary & Head

Dr. B.R. AMBEDKAR OPEN UNIVERSITY
HYDERABAD- 500 033 (A.P.)

DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION

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NATIONAL SEMINAR

ON

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION STRENGTHS AND CHALLENGES

(Sponsored by RAJIV VIDYA MISSION (SSA), HYDERABAD, A.P.)

On Friday, the 08th MARCH, 2013 at 03.30 PM

E-Class Room, STML Building,
University Campus, Road No.46, Jubilee Hills, Hyderabad

Chief Guest

Prof. A. SUDHAKAR

Registrar, Dr. BRAOU

President of the function

Prof. N. VENKATANARAYANA

Director (Academic) & Dean I/c (FoE), Dr. BRAOU

Dr. M.T.V. NAGARAJU
Organising Secretary & Head

PP46

Dr. B. R. AMBEDKAR OPEN UNIVERSITY, HYDERABAD
National Seminar on
INCLUSIVE EDUCATION – STRENGTHS AND CHALLENGES
(Sponsored by Rajiv Vidya Mission (SSA), Hyderabad, Andhra Pradesh)

Day –I (07-03-2013)

Session –III: Role of Apex Bodies, Central and State Governments, NGO's and Universities on Inclusive Education

Time: 3.45 PM to 5.00 PM

Venue: E-Class Room, STML Building, BRAOU

Chairperson: Dr. S. G. R. Prakash, SRC, AYJNIHH, Secunderabad

Rapporteur: Dr. Santhi Prakash, SRC, AYJNIHH, Secunderabad

SLNo.	Title of the Paper	Name of the Presenter/s	Page No
1.	Strengths and challenges of Right to Education Act 2009	Mr. G.R. Sudhakar, Counsellor, BRAOU	
2.	International Perspectives on the goals of Universal Basic and Secondary Education with Special reference to India	Duvvuri V. Naga Pradeep, HYDERABAD	
3.	Inclusive Education In India	Dr. G. Paul Ratnakar, & M. Nagaraju Dr. BRAOU, Hyderabad.	
4.	Role of Apex Bodies, Central and State Governments, NGO's and Universities on Inclusive Education	MD. Mohammad, MakthalMandal, Mahabubnagar (A.P.)	
5.	Implementation of inclusive education in India	Are Srinivasa Reddy OU, Hyderabad	
6.	Role of Apex bodies, Central and State Governments, NGO's and Universities on inclusive education	T. Sudhakar, & T. Sharon Raju, IASE, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam	
7.	Inclusive education in India: An overview	Dr. M. Ramesh & Mr. V. Harihara Prasad DU, Kuppam.	
8.	Inclusive Education in Indian Context	K. Sekhar Reddy, P. Sreenivasulu, YVU, Kadapa, & K. Padma, Kurnool	
9.	National level practices on education of children with disabilities	Dr.N.Venkateswarlu, Villipuram(Tamil Nadu) & Dr. G. Ranga Swamy, SKU, Anantapur	
10.	Role of NGOs, implementation of the inclusive education – A case study of CBR network, Bangalore	Dr. V. Govinda Reddy SKU, Anantapur	
11.	Policies concerning education of children with disabilities	Dr. K. Venkata Reddy & Prof. D. Chenna Reddy, SK.U, Anantapur	
12.	Education of differently abled children: Interventions of SSA	Dr. Mushtaq Ahmed I. Patel & mohasina Anjum Ansari, DDE, MANUU, Hyderabad	46

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY: NEEDS, CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

P. VIJAYA BHASKAR

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The readiness for acceptance of inclusion varies across countries and continents of the world. While countries within the advanced economies have gone beyond categorical provisions to full inclusion and most developing and under developed countries are still grappling with the problem of making provisions for children with special needs especially handicaps, even on mainstreaming basis. This paper attempts to highlight and examine the concept of inclusion and the prospects it holds, for special education practice in the 21st century. In addition, the paper discusses the challenges of inclusion while reflecting upon the ground reality. This paper describes the developments in the theory, policy and practice of inclusive education in the global perspective particularly in India. It also focuses the progress in the development of an inclusive system of education which in responding to the diversity of learners which minimizes exclusion for all. It also presents special needs of inclusive education and the societal awareness on the needs of inclusive education.

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: VISUAL IMPAIREMENT AND READING HABITS

D. VENKATA RAO,

Lecturer in Library Science, Jawahar Bharati Degree College, Kavali – 524 201, Nellore District

DR. K.V.N.L. SEETHA KUMARI,

Lecturer & Counsellor – BRAU - J.B. Centre, Jawahar Bharati College, Kavali – 524 201, Nellore District

The paper proposes to describe what Inclusive Education is with special reference to Visual Impairment and Reading Habits. It mentions the negative effects of disability on the individual and society. It categorises various physical and cultural disabilities.

It defines what Visual Impairment is and mentions the various corrective measures in this regard. It describes the relation between Visual Impairment and Reading Habits. Finally it describes some important steps to be taken with regard to the students with Visual Impairment. The paper closes with the description of the teachers Role which has a great impact in making the Visual Impaired students skilful and self confident.

EDUCATION OF DIFFERENTLY ABLED CHILDREN: INTERVENTIONS OF SSA

Dr. MUSHTAQ AHMED I. PATEL* & MOHASINA ANJUM A. ANSARI**

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A rose is still a rose, when it loses a petal. A tree may lose some leaves, but it is still useful. Likewise, a human being can still be useful despite the loss of a physical faculty. Helen Keller says that the most unfortunate person in society is one who has sight but no vision. In order to understand the abilities of person with disabilities, one needs to have a broad vision of humanistic values. An inclusive society needs the support of parents, teachers, professionals and other community members. The term differently abled children has replaced disabled children, because each individual is bestowed with some or the other potentialities. But, to understand the concept of disability the definition given by the American Heritage Dictionary of English Language can be examined, “a disadvantage or deficiency, especially a physical or mental impairment that interferes with or prevent normal achievement in a particular area or something that hinders or incapacitates”. The present paper tries to find out the population of disabled people in India in different disability categories. A mention of disability services in India during pre independence era, post independence era, DPEP. It is well known fact that the schools have an important role to play for training of differently abled children and the onus is rested with the government to take up new initiatives. The schemes like SSA have played an important role for education of this group in the present times. The paper attempts to explore services improvement of integrated education taken up under SSA and attempts to give objectives, scope, and intervention etc. This will be of great help for policy makers and planner as they are working for universalisation of elementary education, which could not be attend without educating this group.